

THE IMPORTANCE OF SULFUR INORGANIC SUBSTANCES

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Annotation: this article mentions the need to accelerate the transformation processes of the industry, arising from the most advanced foreign experiments, in order to create a solid basis for the sustainable development of all directions of the chemical industry in the long term.

Key words: Educational Directions, SULFUR, chemical industry, surgi drug, raw materials.

Аннотация: в данной статье упоминается о необходимости ускорения процессов трансформации отрасли, вытекающих из самых передовых зарубежных экспериментов, с целью создания прочной основы для устойчивого развития всех направлений химической промышленности в долгосрочной перспективе.

Ключевые слова: Образовательные направления, СЕРА, химическая промышленность, хирургический препарат, сырье.

In recent years, the potential of the chemical industry should provide stable growth dynamics for about 3-5 years.

Priority is given to projects carried out with the participation of private and foreign investors, which provide for the deep processing of local raw materials resources and the organization of inter-sectoral cooperation, the production of exportbop and import substitutes. Step by step, involving international experts and companies, exceptionally on the basis of direct negotiations, should be developed in close connection with the advanced international trends in the long-term development of the chemical industry, as well as Educational Directions and educational programs, project solutions for the construction of a material and technical base of the scientific cluster(academic buildings, laboratory facilities, residential

Our republic is rich in natural fossils. It is necessary to read and process the useful wealth of Mahaliy. For example, when we see compounds containing sulfur, sulfur itself is common in nature. Sulfur is present in the body of animals and plants, since it is part of protein molecules. The organic compounds of sulfur are contained in oil. Its compounds are important. The most important natural compounds are sulfides of metals and salts of sulfuric acid: FeS₂-iron kolchedane, that is, pyrite; ZNS-zinc Aldate; PbS-lead flash; HgS-kinovar, CaSO₄·2H₂O -gips, Na₂SO₄·10H₂O-glauber tuzi, MgSO₄·7H₂O taxir tuz.

Sulfur is an element that has been used for many purposes since ancient times. It is an integral component of many healthcare to industrial sectors. Sulfur is widely used in industry and agriculture. About half of the sulfur mined is spent on obtaining sulfuric acid. Sulfur is used in the vulcanization of rubber, in which the thoroughness and elasticity of rubber increases. Sulfur powder sulfur is also used in the fight against Vine and Acorn diseases, to obtain ammunition, matches. In medicine, sulfur surkov drugs are prepared for the treatment of skin diseases.

Sodium sulfate and sulfite salts are important. In medicine, crystalline hydrate (glauber's salt) containing $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is used as a surgi drug. In the production of Soda and glass, anhydrous sodium sulphate is used. Currently, sodium sulfite is used in many industries and for household needs:

- 1.Used for the analysis, determination and production of tellurium and niobium salts for solution preparation;
 - 2.Artificial fiber stabilizer, fabric bleach, photo maker, deoxidizer for building bleach, lignin paper cleaner are used as fixers.
 - 3.Used as a general analytical reactive and light-sensitive resistance material;
 - 4.The printing and dyeing industry prevents the local oxidation of cotton fiber as a deoxidizer and bleaching agent used in the preparation of various cotton fabrics and affects the strength of the fiber and improves the whiteness of the maturing substance.
 - 5.To ' stabilizer for artificial fibers is used by the textile industry, removing traces of chlorine after bleaching fabrics in the textile industry, removing sulfur from viscose fibers after spinning, and as bleach.
 - 6.It is used in the electronic industry to produce sensitive resistors.
 - 7.It is used in the treatment of wastewater, wastewater containing chromium, for treatment;
 - 8.It is used in the food industry as a bleaching agent, preservative, emollient and antioxidant, is used in pharmaceutical synthesis and in the production of dehydrated vegetables as a reducing agent.
 - 8.Cellulose is used to produce sulfite ether, sodium thiosulfate, organic chemicals, bleached fabrics, etc;
 - 9.For the preparation of sulfur dioxide in the laboratory, it is used as a sulfurizing and sulfomethylating agent in chemical production.
- Currently, sodium sulfite is very versatile in its reactive properties and is widely used in various industries. Using local raw materials, it is necessary to study the most desirable methods of synthesis of sodium sulfite.

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